

NITROGEN FERTILIZERS

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Nitrogenous fertilizers are organic and inorganic substances that contain nitrogen and are used as a source of nitrogen nutrition for plants, a source of nitrogen nutrition for plants. Nitrogen fertilizers were produced in the chemical industry in 1914–18 after the industrialization of the synthesis of ammonia from atmospheric nitrogen and hydrogen. It was produced for the first time in Uzbekistan in 1940 at the Chirchik Electrochemical Combine. Fergana Nitrogen Fertilizer Plant, Navoiy Chemical Combine produces the main types of Nitrogen fertilizers. The annual capacity of the chemical industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the production of nitrogen fertilizers is 2.8 mln. t (1012.1 thousand t of nitrogenous fertilizers were produced in 1995 .

Types of nitrogen fertilizers

Nitrogen fertilizers include organic (manure, peat, compost), mineral (ammonium nitrate, ammonium sulfate, urea and aqueous ammonia) and green fertilizers (blue mass of lupine, seradella, etc.) is divided. Ammonia and nitric acid are the main raw materials in the production of nitrogen fertilizers. Nitrogen fertilizers are the best means of increasing the productivity of agricultural plants in the barren zone, wet areas of the forest-steppe zone, and irrigated farming zone. Plants often extract nitrogen from mineral compounds, mainly nitrate and ammonium salts. Nitrogen in mineral nitrogen fertilizers can be in ammonia, ammonia-nitrate, nitrate and amide forms. Nitrogen contained in these fertilizers is easily absorbed by plants and its effect is quickly felt. Ammonium nitrate and urea are the main amount of nitrogen fertilizers used in the irrigated farming region. Ammonium fertilizers (nitrogen in the form of NH_3) include ammonium sulfate, ammonium chloride, ammonium bicarbonate, anhydrous ammonia, aqueous ammonia, ammonia. Ammonium nitrogen contained in ammonium sulfate is better retained in the soil than nitrogen in the form of nitrate, which is not absorbed by the soil, and is washed away less. Ammonium nitrate is mainly produced in granular form; under the influence of this fertilizer, the soil environment becomes weakly acidic. Nitrate fertilizers

(nitrogen in the form of NO_3) include sodium, calcium, and potassium salts. Nitrate fertilizers are physiologically alkaline, they give good results if they are used in soils with an acidic environment. Amide fertilizers (nitrogen in the form of NH_2) include urea (urea), include urea-formaldehyde fertilizers. Urea is the most effective nitrogen fertilizer in irrigated agriculture. Urea-formaldehyde fertilizers are not washed out of the soil layer, they slowly dissolve in the soil. The rate of nitrogen fertilizers depends on soil and climate conditions, biological properties of plants, the amount of organic fertilizers applied to the soil, etc. The increase in plant productivity when using nitrogen fertilizers is different, and this indicator depends on how the soil is treated, the type of crop being grown and other factors. Experiments conducted in field conditions show that cotton yield can increase by 13.5–15.7 s per hectare and even more when nitrogen fertilizers are used. In order for the productivity to be 37.4–39.8 s per hectare, it is necessary to fertilize the cotton field in the amount of 250–300 kg of pure nitrogen per hectare.

Ammonium nitrate

Ammonium nitrate, ammonium nitrate - colorless, crystalline substance, hygroscopic. Density 820 kg/m^3 . The melting point is $169.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, it dissolves well in water, which absorbs heat (when 1 g of salt dissolves in 1 g of water, the temperature drops from 15 to $-10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Ammonium nitrate is obtained by treating dilute nitric acid with ammonia. A, B and V brands are produced in CIS countries. Brands A and B are used in the manufacture of explosives (ammonites) in industry. Ammonium nitrate grade V is the most common fertilizer with a strong effect on productivity and contains 34% pure nitrogen. It is applied to the ground as the main fertilizer before planting crops and during the growing season, especially in the cultivation of cotton. Ammonium nitrate is highly hygroscopic, so it hardens by absorbing moisture during storage. Therefore, it should be stored in moisture-proof bags in dry rooms. Ammonium nitrate is produced in granular form with the addition of various substances to reduce moisture absorption and solidification. Ammonium nitrate in this case is well preserved. Ammonium nitrate fertilizer is produced at Chirchik, Fergana, and Navoi chemical plants (see Nitrogen fertilizers).

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